

Role of Flux Density (Wavefunction Gradient Wavefunction) in Quantum Bound States

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In the literature (1) it has been noted that $(d/dx W)/W - (d/dx W^*)/W^*$ represents a classical velocity, where W is the wavefunction. For bound states, this expression is zero, yet $(d/dx W)/W$ seems to play the role of density flux as $d/dx (WW) = 2W d/dx W$. When multiplied by E , the energy, it becomes an energy flux as there is constant energy at each point x . In this note, we wish to consider some examples related to this flux. In particular, for the case of $V(x)=0$ (no potential), the flux becomes a solution of the time independent Schrodinger equation. This and other considerations may suggest that periodic type functions (possibly related to photons or phonons) when multiplied by the wavefunction W , can lead to a new, higher energy wavefunction. We also consider the role of energy flux as it relates to discrete energy levels in quantum mechanics.

The Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

In quantum mechanics, $\exp(iEt)$ represents time dependence in the Schrodinger time independent equation. This sometimes leads to a static picture, although time seems to be important even in this time-independent picture. First, there is the period $1/E$ during which, we argue, there is cycling through various "plane wave" or quasiparticle momentum states (2). If a classical period exists in the system, such as in the case of the harmonic oscillator, one would expect $1/E$ to be related to this, as it is. Furthermore, it appears there are fluxes in the quantum system, even if these represent an average. A main flux considered in this note is: $(d/dx W)/W$ which is linear in the momentum of plane waves $(\sum_p p \cos(px)) / [\sum_p p \sin(px)]$. Another flux is $(d/dx)^3 W/W$ which also appears in calculations of the gradient of pressure. We also consider dW/dE as an energy flux to see if it leads to any results.

The Case of $V(x)=0$

For a quantum particle in a box, one can have solutions of $\sin(kx)$ where $k=2\pi n/L$, where L is the size of the box and $\pi=3.14$. Interestingly $\sin(kx)\cos(kx)$ is also a solution and is proportional to $k\sin(kx)\cos(kx)$ or $W(d/dx W) = WW (d/dx W)/W = \text{density}(x) u(x)$ i.e. a flux. This is a matter flux, but if multiplied by E , energy, it becomes an energy flux. Consider:

$$(d/dx)(d/dx) W = 3 (d/dx W) (d/dx)(d/dx)W + W (d/dx)^3 W \quad ((1))$$

The first term on the right side seems to show flux carrying classical kinetic energy $.5mv(x)v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x)=E$. The second, with terms $p^3 \cos(px)$ seems to represent an internal kinetic energy flux. For the case of $V(x)=0$ this internal energy flux is the same as the

collective one represented by the first term on the right side of ((1)) . Thus, the Hamiltonian, $(-1/2m) (d/dx)d/dx$ operation on the flux Wd/dxW yields a kinetic energy flux and kinetic energy is the only energy in the problem and so this is an energy flux. But:

$H(Wd/dxW) = E Wd/dxW$ implies that $W d/dxW$ is a solution of the Schrodinger equation, i.e. represents a higher energy wavefunction. This is interesting because one sees a new wavefunction formed from the product of W , a lower energy wavefunction and $d/dx W$ which is also a periodic type of function if W is one. This may suggest more general combinations of W with periodic type functions.

The Product of the Wavefunction with a Periodic Type of Function

In a previous note (2), it was argued that the time independent Schrodinger equation represented cycling with a period of $1/E$. It was argued the wavefunction could be written as a Fourier series, where p represented physical momentum i.e. $W = \sum \text{over } p \text{ } f_p \sin(px)$. It was also argued that $V(x)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation could be written as the product of two Fourier series leading to:

$$p^2/2m \sum f_p \sin(px) + [\sum_{k,j} \text{with } k+j=p \text{ } V_k f_j] \sin(px) = E \sum f_p \sin(px) \quad ((1.5))$$

This holds for each p , showing that each plane forms a resonance with the potential, with the same cycling frequency E . Thus, $V(x)$ multiplied by $W(x)$ can be thought of as an interaction creating a wavefunction. We argue that such a picture is physical, i.e. that physical $\exp(ikx)$ from the potential interacts with a zitterbewegung type quantum particle in a state $\exp(ijx)$. If such is the case, one might consider a function $g(x)W(x)$ where $g(x)$ also represents an oscillating type of object, such as a photon or phonon. Traditionally, it seems that quantum mechanical atoms shed photons as electrons change from one state to another by emitting a photon, but the photon is considered in terms of energy and momentum conservation. The frequency of the photon does not seem to enter physically into the problem. In this note, we try to argue that the frequency of a photon or phonon, which is physical, is important to the problem because it allows for the formation of a resonance like $V(x)W(x)$. Applying the time independent Schrodinger equation to $g(x)W(x)$ leads to:

$$2 (d/dx g(x)) (d/dx W)/W + (d/dx)(d/dx)g = (E_1-E_0) g \quad ((2))$$

Here E_0 is the energy of the state represented by W and E_1 by $g(x)W(x)$. Thus, one sees that conservation of energy (E_1-E_0) is important in the problem, but also that the function $g(x)$ may represent a polynomial with peaks and troughs, i.e. a periodic type function. This should be the case for the oscillator problem for example, where $W(x)=C\exp(-ax^2)$. Thus, it seems that $g(x)$ may represent a periodic type object such as a photon or phonon. Phonons are absorbed and emitted by qubit systems.

Energy Flux dW/dE and Discrete Energy Levels

An important result of the time-independent Schrodinger equation is the fact that solutions are orthogonal and energy levels discrete. This follows from mathematical properties of the eigenvalue differential equation and boundary conditions. This math is important, but does not give a physical picture, it seems. Consider:

$$(E-V) = (-1/2m) [(d/dx)(d/dx) W]/W \quad \text{and} \quad (E+b-V) = (-1/2m) [(d/dx)(d/dx) W_1]/W_1$$

Here, b is an infinitesimal amount. Subtracting one from two above gives:

$$b = (-1/2m) [(1/W_1) d/dx d/dx W_1 - (1/W) d/dx d/dx W]$$

At this point, one might think that W_1 and W could be infinitesimally related.

Multiplying by WW_1 gives:

$$bWW_1 = (-1/2m) [W d/dx d/dx W_1 - W_1 d/dx d/dx W] \quad ((3))$$

The right hand side can be written as: $d/dx [W d/dx W_1 - W_1 d/dx W]$

Integrating both sides of ((3)) and having W and W_1 vanish at the boundaries gives:

$\int dx W(x)W_1(x) = 0$ i.e. the two functions are orthogonal.

This type of argument is used often in the literature.

The question arises as to whether one can have solutions for E and $E+b$ where b is infinitesimal. So far, it seems that the only restriction is that W and W_1 be orthogonal.

$W(x)$ may be positive throughout a region (say for the ground state of an oscillator). Then $W_1(x)$ must be positive and negative if $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ are orthogonal in the region, so $W_1(x)=0$ at some point.

Given that one assumes there is a W for each E , then:

$W_1(x) = W(x, E+b) = W(x) + b d/dE W(x, E)$. Here b is infinitesimal so for $W_1(x)$ to be 0 and $W(x)$ not zero, there is a contradiction. Thus, it seems that one cannot have continuous energy values, leading to the idea of discrete energy levels.

This can also be seen using: $W_1(x) = W + b d/dE W$, where $d/dE W$ is a kind of energy flux (if multiplied by W). Then:

$$WW = W d/dx d/dx d/dE W - (dW/dE) d/dx d/dx W$$

Assuming that one can interchange d/dE and $(d/dx)(d/dx)$ and that $mv dv/dE = 1$ from conservation of classical energy and $(-1/2m) d/dx d/dx W = WW \cdot 5 m v(x)v(x)$ yields:

$W = W + W \frac{dW}{dE} (\frac{1}{2m} \nabla^2 W)$ which is a contradiction. Thus, W and W_1 cannot be infinitesimally related.

(The contradiction can already be seen at an earlier stage. Consider:
 $\frac{d}{dx} [W \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W - \frac{d}{dE} W \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W]$
 Integrating both sides over dx yields 0 for the right hand side, but b on the left hand side, but a b^2 correction.)

An alternative way to see this, is to note that $W(x)$ and $W_1(x)$ must differ as functions of x more than infinitesimally if they are to be orthogonal. This means that there must be very large flux $\frac{d}{dx} W(x)$ differences if one changes the energy very slightly (by b). It seems this would not happen as $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$. The various $\sin(px)$ which model zitterbewegung states govern to a large degree the wavefunction and tiny energy changes, it seems would not yield large flux changes in the system. Thus, there is a perhaps also a somewhat physical reason that one cannot have solutions for all E if one considers a quantum bound state composed of $\sin(px)$ quasiparticle states with weights of f_p (and $W(x)$).

The problem with energy flux $\frac{dW}{dE}$ seems to exist already for the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Consider taking $\frac{d}{dE}$ of:

$$(-\frac{1}{2m}) \frac{1}{W} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + V = E$$

$$(-\frac{1}{2m}) (-\frac{1}{W^2} W) \frac{dW}{dE} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + (-\frac{1}{2m}) (\frac{1}{W}) \frac{d}{dE} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W = 1$$

This seems to lead to:

$1 = W$ which is a contradiction. Thus, it does not seem one can have fluctuations in E , while still preserving the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Again, this might be due to the underlying structure of plane waves (or quasiparticles) given by $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$. Apparently, this only allows for very sharp energy resonances.

Discrete Energy Levels and Cycling

To perhaps understand discrete energy levels somewhat, one can consider the idea of cycling (2). It was suggested that $\exp(iEt)$ represents a resonance in which the quantum bound system is cycling through the different momentum states in the wavefunction $W = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$. This cycling occurs in such a way that each plane wave is involved in a resonance with a time cycle of E as described by ((1.5)). Thus, consider a solution to the time independent Schrodinger equation, namely W . The plane wave states are in are in a resonance with frequency E . Now imagine that one believes there is a solution for $E+b$, where b is infinitesimal. Let us also imagine that because b is tiny $W_1 = W + dW$ where dW is very small. Now,

$$H(W_1) = H(W+dW) = EW + H(dW)$$

Then $H(dW)=E(dW)$, but this gives $H(W1)=EW1$. One is back to W . The problem seems to be that W is already in resonance and so any dW must be in the same E frequency resonance to have an overall cycling resonance. Otherwise, one is mixing two different cycling resonances. Thus, the energy levels must be discrete. In other words, it is argued that microscopic resonance considerations are responsible for the discrete energy levels.

Conclusion

In this note, we have attempted to consider some ideas related to the fluxes $W d/dx W$ and $d/dE W$. It seems an oscillatory function $g(x)$ multiplied by $W(x)$, the wavefunction, can lead to a higher energy level wavefunction. This may be related to the idea of a photon or phonon with a frequency exciting an atom or qubit. Secondly, we have attempted to consider why quantum bound states have discrete energy levels. Using the idea of energy flux $d/dE W$, one obtains contradictions if one assumes one can move from a solution W, E to $W+dW$ and $E+b$ where b is infinitesimal. We have also examined this in terms of cycling to see that for this picture to be consistent $dW=bW$ which means one essentially obtains the same solution E, W when one normalizes again.

References

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